

Green synthesis of Au/AgNPs and their photodegradation of organic dyes in aqueous solution

Jolly Pal^a, Manas Kanti Deb^{a*} and Jayant Kumar Sircar^b

^aSchool of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur-492 010, Chhattisgarh, India

^bANC Division, National Metallurgical Laboratory (NML), Jamshedpur-843 017, Jharkhand, India

E-mail : debmanas@yahoo.com

Abstract : A green synthesis of bimetallic [gold/silver nanoparticles (Au/AgNPs)] has been done by microwave irradiation in the presence of reducing and stabilizing agents. Au/AgNPs were analyzed using UV-Visible spectroscopic technique, transmission electron microscope (TEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD). The Au/AgNPs prepared in this way were uniform. Appearance of surface plasmon band indicated the formation of NPs. Highly monodisperse stable Au/AgNPs were obtained within few minutes of microwave irradiation. Through TEM, Au/AgNPs were observed to be spherical. Actual size of Au/AgNPs was observed by XRD technique. The photocatalytic degradation of organic dyes (alizarin red S, bismark brown R, eosin and methyl violet) assisted by metal Au/AgNPs were investigated in aqueous solution under irradiation by UV lamp. This method has great potential in photocatalytic degradation using Au/AgNPs. The Au/AgNPs were found to be good catalyst for photocatalytic degradation of organic dyes from aqueous solution.

Keywords : Photodegradation, alizarin red S, bismark brown R, eosin, methyl violet.

Introduction

Organic dyes belong to an important class of materials widely used in textile and many other industries, while the hazardous effects of organic dyes in waste water have been a major concern. Alizarin red-S is widely used in woven fabrics, wool, cotton textiles^{1,2}. The chemical structure of alizarin red-S is shown in Fig. 1. Bismark brown R, whose chemical structure is shown in Fig. 2, is a certified biological stain, for microscopy, histology and cytology, and also used in textile industries³. Eosin is used in the fields of dyeing, printing, leather, printing ink and fluorescent pigment, etc. Eosin is used in paint and dye industries because of its vivid colour⁴. The chemi-

Fig. 2. Chemical structure of bismark brown R.

cal structure of eosin is illustrated in Fig. 3. Methyl violet (MV) is used in textiles, paints and printing inks manufacturing⁵. In biomedical fields, MV is the active ingre-

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of alizarin red-S.

Fig. 3. Chemical structure of eosin.

dient in Gram's biological stain for bacteria classification⁶. Sometimes, it can be used as moderate-class disinfectant but found to be very poisonous to most animals. Inhalation of MV may also cause irritation to respiratory tract, whereas ingestion causes irritation to gastrointestinal tract⁵. The chemical structure of MV is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Chemical structure of MV.

Conventional treatment methods, such as adsorption are often inadequate and inappropriate for removing large amounts of organic pollutants from waste water streams; it is also noteworthy that adsorption is a non-destructive method, which simply transfers pollutants from one phase or substance to another⁷⁻⁹. In contrast, the treatment method of photo-catalytic degradation has the capability of converting toxic molecules into non-toxic compounds. In last decade photocatalytic degradation using metal nanoparticles (NPs) has been shown to be effective for destruction of pollutants. The increasingly demanding request for new catalysts in terms of recovery, regeneration and reuse, has attracted the attention of a significant part of the scientific community¹⁰. In this context, nanosized catalysts have recently become a hot topic of interest because of their high surface area that results in outstanding activity³. As particle size decreases by reaching nanodimension, gradual transformation, from the bulk in the solid-state to the molecular level occurs. A homogeneous catalysis, where the catalyst is in the same phase as the reactants, is generally accepted by chemists. One

of their attractive properties is that all catalytic sites are accessible because the catalyst is generally a soluble metal complex. Homogeneous catalysts have a number of other advantages such as high selectivity, better yield, and easy optimization of catalytic systems by modification of ligand and metals. They are widely used in a number of commercial applications, but the difficulty of catalyst separation from the final product creates economic and environmental barriers to broadening their scope. Despite their advantages and their wide use in a number of applications, many homogeneous catalytic systems have not been commercialized because of the difficulty encountered in separating the catalyst from the final reaction product. Removal of trace amounts of catalyst from the end product is essential since metal contamination is highly regulated, especially by the pharmaceutical industry. Even with the extensive and careful use of various techniques such as distillation, chromatography, or extraction, removal of trace amounts of catalyst remains a challenge.

By tailoring the size and shape of metal NPs one can alter and enhance their intrinsic properties for diverse applications. Several NPs such as silver and gold have been used for photocatalytic destruction of organic pollutants in waste water^{10,11}. The preparation of metal NPs is usually based on the reduction of a metal salt in the presence of a reducing agent and a stabilizer^{11,12}. Many types of NPs such as metal, metal oxide and metal sulphide NPs have been prepared in solution and on solid supports to catalyze a multitude of reactions, including reduction, oxidation, cross coupling and hydrogenation with application ranging from organic synthesis to pollutant removal and energy production^{10,11}. NPs properties have been utilized in electronic, optical and catalysis applications. Bimetallic NPs are being thoroughly studied for the unique advantages that they offer over their single-metal counterparts, for example, in enhanced catalytic activity and selectivity, fine tuning of optical properties, magnetism, gene delivery and electronic materials. Bimetallic NPs sometimes show unique behaviour because of their modified electronic structure and optical properties. Depending on their distribution mode of two elements, different types of alloy such as random alloy, alloy with intermetallic compounds, cluster-in-cluster and core-shell structures can be obtained. The presence of two metallic elements often causes an improvement in

physical and chemical properties¹³. Bimetallic NPs are of wide interest since they lead to many interesting size dependent electrical, chemical and optical properties. A number of methods have been used to prepare the bimetallic NPs, including alcohol reduction¹³, citrate reduction¹⁴, polyol processes¹⁵, borohydride reduction¹⁶, solvent extraction-reduction¹⁷, sonochemical methods¹⁸, photolytic reduction¹⁹, radiolytic reduction²⁰, laser ablation²¹, and biological programming²². They are particularly important in the field of catalysis since they often exhibit better catalytic properties than their monometallic counterparts^{12,23,24}. The structure of bimetallic combinations depends mainly on the preparation conditions and the miscibility of the two components. Bimetallic NPs have been found to have better catalytic activities than pure metal NPs¹¹.

In this paper a simple, green and efficient route to preparing bimetallic gold/silver nanoparticles (Au/AgNPs), is described. Bimetallic NPs were prepared by a microwave irradiation procedure. NPs were characterized by UV-Visible spectroscopy, transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique. The catalytic behaviour of bimetallic NPs towards organic dyes is also given in detail in this paper. Photocatalytic degradation of alizarin red S, bismark brown R, BG, eosin and MV by using Au/AgNPs, are described.

Experimental

Preparation of Au/AgNPs :

The synthesis of Au/AgNPs was carried out by mixing specific volume 5 ml of HAuCl_4 solution (0.0001 M) to 5 ml of the AgNO_3 solution (0.0001 M). To the above solutions, 2 ml aqueous solution of glucose (0.5 M) and 0.2 ml of PVP 1% (w/v) were added in a 50-ml conical flask to obtain a homogeneous reaction mixture. Then the flasks were placed on the turntable of the microwave oven. The mixtures were irradiated at a power of 450 watt for a total of 3 min duration. However, the above irradiation process was carried out discontinuously in 30 s installments in order to prevent an increase of pressure. After complete irradiation, appearance of colours indicates the formation of Au/AgNPs. The above prepared Au/AgNPs, was cooled to room temperature for characterization.

Procedure for treatment of some organic species with nanoparticles :

The photocatalytic degradation studies were carried out by employing UV-radiation. Typically 0.1 ml NPs were added to 20 ml of aqueous solution of organic dyes (10 mg/L) in a 100-ml beaker. A magnetic stirrer was used during photocatalysis for good mixing of the photocatalysts in the solution. The mixture was irradiated, for different timings, with 15 W Hg Philip UV lamp (Philips, India) inside the photo-reactor. The magnitude of photocatalytic decomposition of alizarin red S, bismark brown R, eosin and MV on the Au/AgNPs were examined at a wavelengths of maximum absorbance (λ_{max}), that is, at 430, 460, 510 and 580 respectively, by UV-Visible spectroscopy.

Results and discussion

Formation of Au/AgNPs :

The advantage of microwave-mediated synthesis over the conventional heating is the improved kinetics of the reaction generally by one or two order of magnitude, due to rapid initial heating and the generation of localized high-temperature zones at reaction sites.

The fine structure of the prepared bimetallic NPs can be observed from their absorption spectra. UV-Visible spectroscopy is a simple and effective tool for the determination of the structure of the synthesized bimetallic NPs.

Fig. 5 shows the absorption spectra of microwave irradiated reduced solution for Au, Ag and Au/Ag NPs. Absorption spectra corresponding to the monometallic components are also given for comparison. It can be seen

Fig. 5. UV-Visible spectra of AgNPs, AuNPs and Au/AgNPs. Varian Carry 50 UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

that the AuNPs shows a surface plasmon band at 520 nm and the solution has purple color. The AgNPs shows a surface plasmon band at 420 nm and the solution has pale yellow color. The absorbance behavior of the bimetallic dispersion is found to be different from that of the mono-metallic components. The molar ratio of metal is 1 : 1. Alloy formation is confirmed by the optical absorption spectra that shows only one surface plasmon peak, and the position of λ_{\max} depends on the composition. The plasmon band has hypsochromic shift.

The TEM image of the Au/AgNPs is shown in Fig. 6. The Au/AgNPs which was obtained when using glucose as reducing and PVP as stabilizing agent under micro-

Fig. 6. TEM image of the Au/AgNPs prepared employing glucose as reducing agent and PVP as stabilizing agent (300 W; 4 min irradiation). Magnification : 13000 \times ; Resolution : 1376 \times 1032 \times 16; Image intensity : Gray value; Accelerating voltage : 70 Kv; Microscope : Morgagni 268; Camera type : Keen View FW.

wave irradiation after 3 min, were nearly uniform and spherical in shape and well dispersed. Fig. 7 show the corresponding particle size distribution histogram of the Au/AgNPs. The size distribution histogram revealed that such Au/AgNPs range from 4–8 nm in size. Approximately 40% of these NPs consist of particles with 6 nm, 30% particles with 5 nm and size of the remaining particles was in the range of 4, 7, 8 nm diameter. It may be noted that all these particles were well separated from each other.

The structure of the prepared Au/AgNPs was characterized by employing X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique as shown in Fig. 8. The average size of the particles were derived from the peak width using the Scherrer equation,

$$d = \frac{0.9\lambda}{B \cos \theta}$$

where, d corresponds to the particle size, λ is the X-ray wavelength, θ is the Bragg's angle and B corresponds to

Fig. 7. Size distributions of the Au/AgNPs synthesized under optimum experimental conditions.

Fig. 8. XRD diffraction pattern for Au/AgNPs. Bruker D8 Advance X-ray diffractometer; Wavelength of X-ray was 0.154 nm (Cu K-alpha); Detector based on silicon strip technology (Bruker-LynxEye detector).

the full width at half maximum (fwhm) of the peak under consideration. The corresponding size of the Au/AgNPs calculated at an equivalent angle (2θ) of 35.20, 40.67, 60.33 and 68.0 were found to be 6.21 nm, 6.28 nm, 6.86 nm and 7.11 nm, respectively. Thus, the Au/AgNPs mean size is estimated to be 7 nm.

Photodegradation of organic dyes :

Several monometallic and bimetallic NPs have been used for photocatalytic degradation of organic dyes in waste water. Alumina-supported ultrafine CeO₂ catalysts prepared by a microemulsion method showed CO oxidation activities²⁵. The photocatalytic activity for the photodegradation of phenol was studied by titanium dioxide NPs, prepared by hydrothermal treatment of microemulsion²⁶. The photocatalytic activity for the photodecolorization of acridine orange was studied by PdNPs¹⁰. To study the photocatalytic activity of the Au/AgNPs the model compounds such as alizarin red S, bismark brown R, eosin and MV were chosen that eventually undergoes photodegradation under UV radiation, in the present work. To study the photodegradation process, solutions of alizarin red S, bismark brown R, eosin and MV were employed with Au/AgNPs under UV irradiation. Process of photodegradation of alizarin red S, bismark brown R, eosin and MV were monitored by the decrease in absorbance of the respective peaks of the organic dyes, due to interaction with Au/AgNPs at 430, 460, 510 and 580 nm. In Fig. 9 the absorption spectra of successive degradation of the alizarin red S, bismark brown R, eosin and MV by using Au/AgNPs are shown. The organic dyes become adsorbed on the surface of the metal NPs and eventually degradation irreversibly. NPs help in

photodegradation of organic dyes under UV irradiation. The magnitude of photocatalytic degradation of organic dyes is high when using bimetallic NPs than the monometallic NPs²⁷⁻³¹. The Au/AgNPs has shown high catalytic activity for alizarin red S, bismark brown R, eosin and MV. The high catalytic activity of Au/AgNPs is probably due to the sequential electronic effect between elements in a particle³².

Conclusions

The characteristic catalytic behaviour of Au/AgNPs has been established by studying the photodegradation of alizarin red S, bismark brown R, eosin and MV under UV radiation. The Au/AgNPs were synthesized in glucose and PVP aqueous solution by a microwave irradiation method. The results obtained from UV-Visible spectroscopy and TEM clearly demonstrated the reduction of Ag⁺ and Au³⁺ in their respective salt solutions. The XRD technique showed the presence of Au/AgNPs with an average size of 7 nm. The microwave irradiation method is simple, versatile and rapid for green synthesis of Au/AgNPs. The characteristic catalytic behaviour of Au/AgNPs was established by studying the degradation of alizarin red S, bismark brown R, eosin and MV in the presence of UV irradiation. It has been authenticated from the study that Au/AgNPs have a tremendous influence on

Fig. 9. UV-Visible spectra for photodegradation of (a) alizarin red S, (b) bismark brown R, (c) eosin, (d) MV by Au/AgNPs in aqueous solution, the time interval between successive measurements are 5 min.

the reaction. The method could be an efficient, highly safe and cost-effective way for the degradation of alizarin red S, bismark brown R, eosin and MV from solutions. The high catalytic activity of Au/AgNPs is probably due to the sequential electronic effect between elements in a particle.

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